

The Role of Social Media in Deepfake Spread and Misinformation Mitigation

TABLE I. VARIABLES AND INDICATOR

Code	Question	Ref
Social Media News Use		
SM1	How often do respondents use social media sites to get news about social, political, or public affairs?	[1]
SM2	You often use social media to stay updated with the latest news or important events?	[2]
SM3	You use social media to find information relevant to your interests or personal needs?	[3]
SM4	I often share news from social media with friends or family	
Instantaneous Sharing of News for Creating Awareness		
IS1	I try to create awareness by sharing news online	[1]
IS2	I want to educate my online friends by sharing news content online	[2]
IS3	I use social media to spread information that can help others understand certain issues.	[3]
IS4	I feel that sharing news instantly on social media is an effective way to spread important information.	
Active Corrective Actions on Fake New		
AC01	I advise the sender of fake news to stop sharing it.	[1]
AC02	I try to make people aware of fake news.	
AC03	I advise the sender of fake news to always crosscheck its authenticity before sharing.	[2]
AC04	I educate the sender of the fake news on ways to authenticate it.	[3]
Passive Corrective Actions on Fake News		
PC1	I report the account which constantly sends fake news to me	[1]
PC2	I block accounts that send me fake news	[2]
PC3	I avoid reading or opening messages from accounts that often spread fake news.	[3]
PC4	I unfollowed accounts that frequently posted fake news on social media.	
Probability to Share Fake News		
PTS1	I often share fake news on COVID-19 because I don't have time to check its authenticity	[1]
PTS2	I share fake news on COVID-19 because I don't have time to check facts through trusted sources.	[2]
PTS3	I shared the news because it seemed interesting, even though I wasn't sure of its veracity.	[3]
PTS4	I sometimes share videos or images that I find interesting even if I don't know whether they are true or not.	
Authenticating News Before Sharing		
AN1	I rely on TV news channels to check the authenticity of any message before sharing it	[4]
AN2	I ask my friends to check the authenticity of any message before sharing it	[5]
AN3	I feel more confident sharing news if I see that it has been validated by other people.	[6]
AN4	I check comments or discussions related to news on social media to ensure their authenticity before sharing them.	[10]
Deepfakes Exposure		

DE1	How frequently do respondents come across deepfakes on (a) social media sites and (b) the Internet (other than social media sites)?	[5]
DE2	I feel like more and more scams are using deepfakes to defraud individuals or organizations.	[8]
DE3	I worry that deepfakes could be used to create conflict or tension in society.	[9]
DE4	I find it difficult to differentiate between real and deepfake videos or images.	
Deepfakes Concern		
SMD1	My social media feed sometimes features marketing messages from ecommerce companies	[3]
SMD2	I follow links to ecommerce websites from my social media accounts	[5]
SMD3	I follow several e-commerce companies on my social media accounts.	[9]
SMD4	I find it difficult to avoid using social media even for short periods of time.	
Inadvertent Deepfakes Sharing		
IDS1	Have respondents ever shared a deepfake without realizing it was fake?	
IDS2	I felt confident that a video was genuine, but later discovered it was a deepfake.	[5]
IDS3	I feel that many people on social media unknowingly share deepfakes without knowing their authenticity.	[6]
IDS4	I deleted or withdrew a post after realizing it was a deepfake.	[7]